

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT : This article covers the history of the origin of artificial intelligence, its development, benefits and harms in human life in military, defense, medicine and other fields.

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The development of humanity, the stability of the country directly depends on the development of artificial intelligence inextricably linked. Therefore, artificial intelligence is usually associated with the capabilities of the human mind: language understanding, teaching, discussing, solving problems, some people are weak in the human factor to make certain inventions in order to further develop the fields and similar opportunities are engaged in creating the system. A simple example is computer chess players and you. Those familiar driverless vehicles, which are not new to us, are the fruit of artificial intelligence. There is a lot of rapidly developing artificial intelligence in the current technology space has an annual history. Its seeds were planted by classical thinkers defined the thinking process of people as mechanical manipulation. As an example it can be noted that to understand whether the machine can really think or no several scientific studies have been carried out. As the basis of these ideas, the 40s of the 20th century. By 1990, the first programmed digital computer working on artificial intelligence was invented is evidence that the machine is based on the essence of mathematical thinking. of the device creation, a number of scientists to analyze the ideas in the field and a certain one in this field. It is no exaggeration to say that it inspired the publication of news. But this period the term was not named after artificial intelligence. First published in 1956 by John McCarthy held at Dartmouth College while holding his first academic position. At the conference, this term was presented to the public under the name "Artificial

Intelligence" and conference participants McCarthy, Minsky, Shannon, Turing and others for decades have become industry leaders. They believe that smartmachines will be around for a long time many investments were attracted in order to develop their projects. In 1973, in response to constant pressure from Congress and criticism from James Lighthill British government to fund research into artificial intelligence stopped, and then came a period of difficulty for this industry. This situation continued for seven years and the Japanese government artificially shut down the industry inspired the intellect to provide billions of dollars, but by the end of the 80s investors completed the financing of the project. By the first decade of the 21st century interest in artificial intelligence has begun to grow and due to investment in this field successful application of new methods to many problems in academia and industry done. For example, the Agency for Advanced Research Projects of the Ministry of Defense in the 1970 developed a number of virtual street map projects. The specialists of this project some virtual voices, such as Alice, were intelligent in 2003, long before Siri they managed to create personal assistants. These works on modern computers particularly in decision support systems and human empowerment automation and formal logic used in developed intelligent search engines became the basis for the principles. Although artificial intelligence is often used in science fiction films. Although they are described as powerful scientific robots in their works, they have their own power on a global scale occupied. The direction of artificial intelligence appeared in our country with a delay of almost 10 years and this corresponds to the first half of the 60s of the 20th century. Nowadays, artificial intelligence is rapidly developing and covers many fields. Widely used by experts in medicine, astronomy and several other fields is being used. But some say that artificial intelligence can communicate with people, imagines an ideal machine that thinks like them. Of course, this is also artificial intelligence derivative, however, is a much more complex and broader concept. We use it daily some

applications on our smartphones and computers are clear examples of artificial intelligence. For example, Google Translate, Yandex Alisa, Siri, various games and other programs we can bring. Only the scope of these applications is smaller and in a certain direction is directed. That is, from the relevant applications depending on the actions you want to perform you use. Currently, artificial intelligence is an algorithm designed to perform various actions, consists of software systems and a number of tasks that can be performed by the human mind can manage. For example, an IBM computer called Deep Blue, created in the 90s we can bring. He defeated the world chess champion Garry Kasparov in history was the first computer. Another bright example of artificial intelligence is the IBM Watson supercomputer and it answers questions in a specific language based on its base. Also Siri, a mobile assistant that has become a constant companion of many people, restores photo programs such as working Prisma can be noted as one of AI's achievements. For now artificial intelligence has become widely popular in almost all of our daily lives covers all aspects. For example, bank cards to residents of Incheon in China there is no need. All processes related to calculations are performed by artificial intelligence is done by clarifying the face. Many people ask, "In which field is artificial intelligence necessary?" if the question arises, directly I can say medicine. After all, in 2020, the COVID-19 virus will not only affect China together, causing a pandemic situation with its virus that has spread all over the world, how many of our doctors are treating our patients infected with this virus themselves also caused them to fall ill with this disease and killed a large number of people. Scientists of the world artificial intelligence tools are modern to fight against this virus a powerful vaccine against this infectious disease through technologies, devices and robotics and used to find medicine. The idea is to protect our doctors from this ridiculous virus. Instead of them, a robot with artificial intelligence is introduced to look after the patients one should be put in the hospital. They quickly went to each sick person he should

measure his temperature, give necessary medicines and reach another patient.

The main reasons for replacing doctors with robots:

1. There is no risk of transmission of the Covid-19 virus. Because it is Robot With the name of the robot, he quickly looks after one patient and so together with another. He manages to get information about the patient's condition.

2. Another main reason is the lack of salary. It is state and non-state

We would not be mistaken if we say that it will be financially beneficial for organizations. Robots that are the fruit of artificial intelligence are the current demand in the viral space. Contact with patients seriously ill with infectious viruses is much more difficult. In these works the demand for medical robots is high. As a result, the lives of many doctors and caused the population's health to be preserved. Artificial intelligence used to detect cancer is now COVID-19. It is also used to find the coronavirus. Software in 34 Chinese hospitals was used, and with its help, more than 32,000 cases were investigated known. Our compatriot from Guzor district, Kashkadarya region in Uzbekistan created a robot working on artificial intelligence in the field of medicine. These robots disinfected intended AI is needed by humans in every field and humans benefit from these robotic system is used for the purposes. However, it cannot be done without risks. Some artificial intelligence there are aspects that pose a threat to human life including artificial intelligence performing tasks and functions faster and at a higher level than human ability possible, and in turn, this will have a serious impact on human employment. Another aspect is artificial due to intelligence, people can have unlimited additions. This is because of anxiety may cause some problems.

In recent years, military security has emerged in the system of international relations is directly and indirectly connected to artificial intelligence in the fields of defense. The explosion of unmanned vehicles was caused by conflicts in world politics causing wars to become more brutal and barbaric. Now military operations

become necessary, the US will manage these operations by launching drones can do it with remote control.

Artificial intelligence has the potential to reduce human involvement in war. Firstly, artificial intelligence is necessary to participate in war and war-related operation can change the allocation of human and machine resources. Secondly Artificial intelligence affects the speed of operations, which is paradoxically decision-making reduces time. It can be said that there is no new military in the last ten year technologies have not received more attention from experts than drones, because drones as the most visible technological tool in the modern wars of the information age is becoming popular. Also in the military successes of the United States of America the role of technological innovations is significant The list of the most valuable companies in the world 10 years ago companies, by this year digital technology companies are 9 out of the Top 10 company is located

Currently, the economic potential of nation states is based on this technolog we can observe that it is lower than the turnover and income of the companies.

According to the Accenture consulting company, 12 have been developpe studies conducted in countries show that by 2035, artificial intelligence will b it can double the global economic growth rate. This increase is threefol characterized by aspect.

Firstly, it is up to 40% of labor productivity due to innovative technologies leading to strong growth and more effective time management related to the workforc allows.

Second, SI creates a new virtual workforce: it's called "intelligent automatio will have the functions of problem solving and self-management

Thirdly, the economy affects various sectors and new incom will also benefit from the spread of innovations that create resources.

According to McKinsey Global Institute observations, artificial intelligence by

203 production of additional economic output in the amount of approximately 13 trillion US dollars it is possible to increase the global GDP, i.e. gross domestic product, by approximately 1.2% annually is carried out at the expense of

In conclusion, it can be said that starting with the history of artificial intelligence, it was written about its benefits and harms in the fields. It is known to everyone that every lease is different there are advantages and disadvantages. Never if we only talk about the damage we cannot grow. If we make good use of its useful aspects, we will be more prosperous in the development of our time adds. But along with these benefits are unemployment, cybercrime, and military risks we need to be careful. It is not surprising that some of these problems will be completely solved in the future.

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